

Dynamic Management of Wireless Sensor Networks using Virtual Objects and a Rule Engine

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Abstract—In this demonstration paper, we present the implementation of a virtualized Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) following a specific software stack called Virtual Object Stack (VOStack). This stack, proposed by the *Horizon Europe (HE)* NEPHELE project, promotes openness and interoperability in the Cloud-to-Edge-to-IoT continuum. The demonstration focuses on the management of a dynamic WSN through VOSTack, the interactions between the physical objects and their virtual counterparts, and a rule engine enabling data processing and alert triggering.

Index Terms—Cloud Continuum, Virtual Object, Web of Things, Wireless Sensor Network, Dynamic Properties, Rule Engine, NEPHELE project.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) typically consist of sensor nodes that are constrained in processing power, memory and energy resources. These nodes are equipped with sensing, processing, and wireless communication units, enabling them to generate and collect large amounts of data. This data is transmitted to more powerful devices, known as gateways, which serve as aggregation and decision-making hubs within the network and act as connection points to edge or cloud servers. WSNs are naturally dynamic, with nodes forming self-organizing networks capable of adapting their connectivity, distributing decision-making processes, and using intelligent routing algorithms and collaborative protocols to respond to external or internal changes.

In the Cloud-to-Edge-to-IoT paradigm, the concept of a virtual object plays a crucial role. It enables the creation of a digital counterpart for any physical device, supporting the development of complex applications and facilitating remote device management. For WSNs, virtual objects support energy efficiency while ensuring interoperability and scalability. Virtualizing unconstrained devices within the WSN, such as gateways, offers numerous advantages, including improved flexibility and easier management of dynamic networks. On the one hand, this virtualization empowers application developers to extend the capabilities of WSNs by adding functionalities to the virtual objects of gateways that are deployed on edge resources. On the other hand, it provides application users with remote access to the WSN and its status while abstracting the complexity of a self-organizing network.

This paper showcases an implementation of a use case defined in the *Horizon Europe (HE)* NEPHELE project: a post-disaster recovery scenario to improve situational awareness [1], [2]. The proposed implementation is built on VOSTack, an IoT and edge computing software stack developed as part

Fig. 1: Application architecture.

of this project [3]. VOSTack is designed in accordance with the standardized Web of Things (WoT) recommendations from the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) [4].

II. IMPLEMENTATION

In this paper, we explore the management of constrained devices by unconstrained devices (Section II-A). We then focus on the interactions between the physical gateway and its virtual counterpart (Section II-B). In the end, we explain the rule engine used by virtual gateways to process sensor data and trigger alerts (Section II-C). A simplified version of the architecture is presented in Figure 1. As shown, we differentiate between constrained and unconstrained devices, as these require distinct handling at both the logical and software perspectives. Unconstrained devices, such as gateways, operate on Raspberry Pi 3, allowing them to support Python and a VOSTack runtime with "almost" unlimited resources.

Alternatively, as already mentioned, constrained devices are limited in terms of computing power, memory, and energy. Since their actions are inherently low-level and their autonomy is minimal, we have deliberately chosen not to create their digital twins: they are instead represented as *Properties* of the physical gateway that manages them. In fact, the W3C

Fig. 2: UML state diagram, from the physical gateway’s perspective. States correspond to node statuses. Actions are exposed in the TD.

WoT framework offers a standardized approach to streamline development and maintenance while ensuring seamless interoperability across applications. At the core of this framework, lies the *Interaction Model* [4]. This model defines three key types of *Affordances* that define how a *Thing* can interact with others: *Actions*, *Events* and *Properties*.

A. Physical gateway level: management of dynamic Properties

In this use case, we have a huge number of sensor nodes that can be added, updated or removed in the field. In the real world, this set is inherently dynamic, so it should also be perceived as dynamic from the gateway’s perspective. That’s why this section treats a node as an element of a dynamic *array-Property* named *nodes*, which is defined and exposed in the Thing Description (TD) of the physical gateway. Taking inspiration from the WoT RFC, we designed an intuitive process to manipulate the array through defined *Actions*. Since *nodes* is modified by *Actions* and external calls, the TD is dynamically refreshed, and the new data is re-exposed by the physical gateway. Subscribers with access to this TD can access the newly exposed data. As shown in Figure 2, these are the main *Actions*:

- `register_new_node()`: **registering a new node with the gateway**, status set to REGISTERED ;
- `deploy_node()`: **deploying a node**, action initiated on the field during the physical deployment of a node, status set to DEPLOYED ;
- `unregister_node()`: **unregistering a node from the gateway**, action performed when the mission has ended, status changed to UNREGISTERED.

Additional node statuses are also used during the gateway’s VOSTack-runtime. Upon receiving new data from the sensors, the status is set to RUNNING by `valid_data_on_next_callback()`. A status

Fig. 3: UML sequence diagram illustrating interactions between physical and virtual gateways.

IN_ERROR is triggered when an unexpected event occurs (e.g., receiving malformed data) or when a time limit is exceeded.

B. Interactions between physical gateway and virtual gateway

The complementarity between MQTT and InfluxDB has already been highlighted e.g., [5]. In a concise manner, temporal data is transmitted via MQTT from constrained devices layer to the cloud layer, where it is stored in a time-series database, like InfluxDB. Our approach follows the same idea, as shown in Figure 3. The physical gateway manages sensor nodes as WoT *Properties*. It collects data and stores it locally in a SQLite database. If the virtual gateway is offline, the physical gateway continues to accumulate data in its SQLite storage. When the virtual gateway is back online, the physical gateway transmits the stored data sequentially, maintaining chronological order. The virtual gateway stores the received data in a cloud-hosted InfluxDB database. After successfully processing each item, the virtual gateway sends an acknowledgment back to the physical gateway, confirming the data has been handled. When receiving this ACK, the physical gateway deletes the corresponding data from its SQLite.

The advantage of this mechanism lies in its ability to preserve data even when communication between the physical and virtual gateways is interrupted. The ACK frees up the memory used on the physical gateway. Furthermore, The virtual gateway evaluates each received data against a set of rules and generates an alert if a violation occurs, forwarding it to the cloud layer to notify users of the risk.

C. Virtual gateway level: threshold-condition rules engine

One main reason for separating physical and virtual gateways is to delegate the responsibility of managing constrained devices to the physical gateways. Therefore, a physical gateway serves as an intermediary. Tasks requiring more resources,

Fig. 4: UML class diagram to represent the threshold-condition rules engine.

i.e. data analysis, are moved to the edge side. Consequently, for anomaly detection, such as *sensor monitoring*, *out-of-range detection*, or *trend and breakpoint analysis*, we opted to implement a rule engine at the virtual gateway level. To implement this detection mechanism and guarantee a flexible and dynamic engine, we wanted to align our approach with the existing literature on Service-Oriented Architectures (SOA) and Business Rule Management Systems (BRMS) [6]. A wide range of tools is available on the market. For instance, *ThingsBoard* appears to be gaining importance in the field of IoT and offers an interesting rule engine [7]. Inspired by this solution but with the aim of accelerating and simplifying its integration into VOSTack, we developed a custom rule engine adapted to data coming from IoT devices.

We developed Python classes to handle what is called an *engine for threshold-condition rules*. A class *Rule* contains three properties:

- *sensor_type*: a sensor type of a constrained device, such as "temperature", "light", "acceleration", etc. ;
- *operator*: a custom Enum that is restricted to: GREATER_THAN, LESS_THAN, EQUAL, GREATER_OR_EQUAL, LESS_OR_EQUAL, built over the native Python module *Operator* ;
- *threshold*: a numerical value against which the sensor value will be compared.

For each rule, we then have a 3-tuple (*sensor_type*, *operator*, *threshold*) used to trigger alert events, propagated to the cloud layer.

This implementation allows chaining the *add_rule()* methods to execute the engine, as illustrated in Figure 5.

III. DEMO DESCRIPTION

During the conference, attendees will be able to watch a video explaining the entire architecture [8]. They will also

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temp_r1 = Rule("temperature", GREATER_THAN, 25)
temp_r2 = Rule("temperature", LESS_THAN, 11)

exec_result = RuleEngine().add_rule(temp_r1)
↳ .add_rule(temp_r2).exec(node_value)

for rule, result in exec_result.items():
    if result:
        exposed_thing.emit_event("new_alert_event",
        ↳ {...})
  
```

Fig. 5: Python example of using the rule engine to trigger alert(s) if the temperature is out-of-range, below 11°C or above 25°C.

have the opportunity to interact with some Pycom devices that we will bring along with a personal computer. Attendees will then be able to adjust live *threshold-condition rules* through a web application deployed on that computer.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this demo, we have presented an implementation of a virtualized WSN using VOSTack, an IoT and edge computing software stack proposed by the *HE NEPHELE* project. We have focused on the management of a dynamic WSN and presented the sequence diagram defining interactions between a physical gateway and its virtual counterpart. We have highlighted the integration of a *threshold-condition rules* engine enabling alerting and data processing deployed on the edge side. For future work, we intend to integrate a routing protocol to enable multi-hop communication within the virtualized WSN.

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